

Reducing Postoperative Reintubations (POR) Through a Risk Assessment Aid

Jacqueline Otake BSN, RN, Caroline Tan BSN, RN and Grace Troyer BSN, RN
Sarah Giron PhD, CRNA, FAANA, Team Leader; Sadeeka Al-Majid PhD, RN, FAAN Team Member

Background/ Significance

Background

- POR is defined as an unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia

Significance

- Incidence of POR: 1.6% in surgical patients
- Financial impact: \$26,718 per incident
- 17 day increase in hospital stay
- 32% increase in patient mortality
- Decreased patient satisfaction throughout the recovery period

Purpose

The purpose is to develop a risk assessment aid based on the most current POR risk factors in order to affect practice change.

Methods

NSQIP Data Analysis

POR Risk Factors Identified by previous DNP Cohorts

- Patient: Age, Race, Gender, Inpatient Status, Smoking, COPD, HTN, CHF, Dependent functional status, Weight loss, Sepsis, SIRS, ASA Status, Elevated BUN, Elevated WBC, Dyspnea
- Surgical: General Anesthesia, Extended length, Blood loss, Surgery type (Cardiac, Neuro, ENT), and Emergent surgery

Delphi Results

- The Delphi study yielded valuable information to assemble the POR risk assessment aid by providing anonymous expert feedback
- 51 carefully selected domestic and international experts were invited to participate in the Delphi study via email
- Experts were required to either be involved in perioperative patient care or have a baseline expertise that is related to POR
- Consensus was reached after three rounds

Risk Assessment Aid

POSTOPERATIVE REINTUBATION (POR) RISK ASSESSMENT AID

POR definition: unplanned placement of an endotracheal tube or similar airway device within 30 days after surgery with general anesthesia (ACS NSQIP, 2015)

RISK STRATIFICATION

MILD	MODERATE	SEVERE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GENERAL ANESTHESIA • SURGICAL BLOOD LOSS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COPD • DYSPNEA • SMOKING • CARDIAC SURGERY • EXTENDED LENGTH OF SURGERY • ASA STATUS 3 OR HIGHER • SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE SYNDROME 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EMERGENT SURGERY • SEPSIS

MODERATE RISK: >2 MILD OR MODERATE RISK FACTORS
HIGH RISK: >3 MILD/MODERATE RISK FACTORS OR 1 SEVERE RISK FACTOR

TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

Moderate risk: chose one treatment during each phase of the perioperative period
High risk: chose > 6 treatments, one during each phase of the perioperative period
*indicates highly supported recommendations

TREATMENT RECOMMENDATIONS CONT.

- **Prior to Admission**
 - Utilize a risk assessment tool
 - Smoking cessation 4 weeks before surgery
 - CXR- consider postponing elective surgery if findings are abnormal
 - Inspiratory muscle training using incentive spirometry 2 weeks before surgery
 - Optimize severe anemia
- **Preoperative**
 - Targeted treatment for pulmonary diseases (CPAP for OSA, Salbutamol for asthma)
 - 30 minutes of prophylactic chest physiotherapy
- **Intraoperative**
 - Type of anesthetic: avoid GA and ETT for high-risk patients
 - Alternatives: regional anesthesia, LMA
 - If GA with ETT is necessary: use low tidal volumes (6-8 ml/kg) with PEEP of 5 cmH₂O.
 - Add recruitment maneuvers and increase PEEP if ventilation is inadequate
 - Neuromuscular blockade: use short/intermediate agents, utilize nerve stimulator to assess the level of block, reverse with Sugammadex*
 - Goal-directed fluid management
- **Postoperative**
 - Prophylactic CPAP or HFNC after major abdominal and thoracic surgery
 - CPAP during the initial postoperative period for OSA patients
 - Mobilization and clearance of secretions: elevate the head of the bed, consider prophylactic mucolytic treatment, encourage early ambulation
 - Ensure adequate pain control: utilize regional anesthesia to decrease the amount of narcotics administered

Discussion

- Risk Assessment Aids are valuable tools to improve patient safety by identifying patients at increased risks of adverse events
- Clinical judgment by itself is not a reliable predictor of risk alone
- Utilizing risk assessment aids results in cost savings and increased provider confidence

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths

- Comprehensive Literature review: 52 articles
- Very low Delphi study attrition rate

Limitations

- The literature search was widened from POR to PPC for recommendations to decrease the incidence
- Duplicate responses during Delphi study
- Recommendations may not be universally applicable to all anesthesia locations

Recommendations

- Implementation of risk assessment aid at a Kaiser facility
- Evaluation of the aid's efficacy using chart audits, educational sessions and surveys

References

